

Role of Digital Marketing in Retail Kitchen Appliances Industry of Hubli

Raj Porwal*
Harshal Borgaon**

Abstract

The use of Internet is increasing continuously and simultaneously the importance of Digital Marketing is also increasing. The marketers want to tap the customers through internet with the help of Digital Marketing. The purpose of this study is to find out the preference of customers towards traditional and Digital Marketing Channels. The paper also attempts to study the Awareness, Presence, Penetration and Reasons for usage or non-usage of digital marketing among the retailers selling Kitchen Appliances in Hubli. The 72 Owners/Managers of Retail Kitchen Appliance stores from Hubli are selected as sample for the study based on convenience sampling. The respondents were surveyed using a Structured Questionnaire. The Major finding of the study was that the majority of the retailers selling Kitchen Appliances in Hubli was aware of Digital Marketing and preferred both Traditional and Digital Marketing channels, but only few were using Digital Marketing.

Keywords: Awareness, Digital Marketing, Kitchen Appliances, Presence and Penetration, Retail, Usage

Introduction to Digital Marketing

Digital Marketing means promotion of products, services, brands, etc. through electronic forms. Digital Marketing is also referred to as 'Online Marketing', 'E-Marketing', and also sometimes as 'Internet Marketing'. Digital Marketing channels helps an organization to promote of products, services, brands, etc. and analyze marketing campaigns and understand what is working and what isn't, typically in real time. Digital marketers monitor what is being viewed, how often and for how long, sales conversions, what content works and doesn't work, etc. Digital Marketing usually involves Internet, but it also include wireless text messaging, Mobile Messaging, Mobile Apps, Podcasts, Electronic Billboards, Digital Television and Radio Channels, etc. Marketing basically can be done conventionally or digitally or even both.

Traditional Vs. Digital Marketing

Digital Marketing differs from Traditional Marketing. Traditional Marketing involves advertisements through Newspaper, Personal Selling. Etc. Digital

marketing involves advertisement through electronic media or platforms like Social Media, Pop-up ads, etc. Traditional Marketing is costlier than Digital Marketing. The effectiveness of the Digital Marketing can be analyzed easily through various online analytical tools, but the effectiveness of the Traditional Marketing is very tough to analyze.

Advantages of Digital Marketing

- Reach large number of people globally.
- Cost of using Digital Marketing is low, when compared to Conventional Marketing.
- Analyzing of effectiveness of the Digital Marketing is easy, through various analytical tools.
- Segmentation, Targeting and Positioning can be done in more effective way.
- Higher Revenue.

Disadvantages of Digital Marketing

- It Requires skills and training.

*Global Business School, Hubli, Mail ID: rajking.porwal@gmail.com

**Asst. Professor, Global Business School, Hubli, Mail ID: harshal@globalbschool.in

- Time consuming for organic traffic.
- Challenging to stand out from the high competition and gain more engagements.
- Security and privacy issues.
- Criticism or Negative reviews can be easily visible to the audience, which may have impact on brand value or brand image of the company.

Kitchen Appliances

Kitchen Appliances means the appliances that are used in the kitchen. The Kitchen Appliances are divided into large Kitchen Appliances and small Kitchen Appliances. The Global Kitchen Appliances Market is expected to grow \$253 billion by 2020. It has an annual growth rate of 6.4% since 2014. In India Kitchen Appliances Market is estimated to be of Rs.21,500 Crores as of 2018. The market is expected to grow at a CAGR of 12% for the next 5 years. Digital Marketing can play a very important role in Kitchen Appliance industry. As there is growth in the number of internet users, there is large scope for marketing of both Large Kitchen Appliances and Small in Kitchen Appliances.

Literature Review

According to Peter.S.H.Leeflang, Peter C Verhoef, Peter Dahlström, and TjarkFreundt, (2014) As there is increase in the internet usage, there is increase in usage of digital marketing. More attention has been given to the various opportunities of digital marketing, with little attention on the challenges. Company home pages, e-mail, and social media are most commonly used Digital platforms. The major challenges faced by businesses are, lack of control, not useful for business, lack of trust, time constraints, etc.

Walid Nabil Iblasi, Dr. Dojanah M.K. Bader and Sulaiman Ahmad Al-Qreini, (2016) says that as large number of people are on social media platforms there is large scope that it might benefit the business. A social media marketing strategy may influence the customers of different age groups and different income groups, but still many businesses don't adapt to social media marketing.

Kalpna Chauhan and Anandan Pillai, (2013) posting frequency of any image, video, etc. on any Digital Marketing platform has an impact on online marketing strategy.

Arun Thamizhvanan, M.J. Xavier, (2013) found that Males are found to have more intention to use online sites than females.

Jean Pierre, Francois Robertson, Mr. Omotayo Abatan,(2017) found that any company or business have objectives for doing any type Digital Marketing; it may be increasing customers, increasing sales, etc. The company or businesses should try to get the outcomes as per their objectives set.

Anupama Nerurkar, (2014) says there are various problems in online trading that are faced by the retailers, such as lack of knowledge of online trading, low scale of online marketing, etc. The retailers are less aware of online marketing and their presence online is very low online. (Heikki, Jayawardhena, and Chanaka Jarvinen, Joel, Tollinen, Aarne, Karjaluoto, (2012) says that Many Businesses prefer Traditional Marketing over Digital Marketing, so they are not upgrading their capabilities to the digital era.

The businesses are not making or increasing their expenditure and using on Digital Marketing, rather they continue to focus on communications with established digital tools. (Patrick De Pelsmacker, Sophie Van Tilburg, and Christian Holthof, 2018) is of opinion that a proper digital marketing plan is to be prepared to use the various digital platforms efficiently and effectively.

Need for Study

The numbers of Internet users are increasing every day and also the number of users on social media, E-commerce, etc. (Walid Nabil Iblasi, Dr. Dojanah M.K. Bader and Sulaiman Ahmad Al-Qreini, 2016). With the advent of e-commerce platforms like Amazon, Flipkart, etc. the online channel is evolving as the fastest growing channel for sales of kitchen appliances (Pakhi Saxena, Shubham Anand, Mukesh Kumar, Raveen Kaur Anand, Saurabh Joshi & Sumit Kumar, 2018). Many retailers prefer Traditional Marketing over Digital Marketing (Heikki, Jayawardhena, and Chanaka Jarvinen, Joel, Tollinen, Aarne, Karjaluoto, 2012). There are various problems in online trading that are faced by the retailers, such as lack of knowledge of online trading, low scale of online marketing, etc. The retailers need to be aware and increase their presence on Digital Marketing Platforms (Anupama Nerurkar, 2014). Businesses have objectives for doing any type Digital Marketing; it may be increasing customers, increasing sales, etc. (Jean Pierre, Francois Robertson, Mr. Omotayo Abatan, 2017). So, after the literature review, it is realized that there is a need to study digital marketing in the retail kitchen appliances.

Research Gap

1. There is very little research that has been done in the field of digital marketing in particularly the kitchenware appliances in retail sector in India.
2. There is no research conducted in the field of digital marketing among the kitchenware appliances in retail sector in Hubli City.

Research Objectives

1. To know the preference of kitchenware retailers between Traditional vs. Digital Marketing Channels in Hubli.
2. To know the awareness of digital marketing among the kitchenware retailers in Hubli.
3. To know the presence and penetration of Digital Marketing among the kitchenware retailers in Hubli
4. To find the reasons for usage or non-usage of digital marketing among the kitchenware retailers in Hubli.

Research Methodology

The study consists of 72 respondents, where the respondents were the managers/owners of the kitchenware retail stores in Hubli. The Primary data of this study was mainly Qualitative in nature.

Research method	: Descriptive research
Research Approach	: Survey Method
Sample Size	: 72 (Census Population)
Population	: Kitchenware Retailers in Hubli (127)
Primary Data	: Structured Questionnaire
Location of research	: Hubli, Karnataka
Statistical tools	: MS Excel & SPSS

Data Analysis

Table 1: Demographics

		Frequency	Percent
Age Group	Below 25 yrs.	2	2.8
	26-35 yrs.	16	22.2
	36-45 yrs.	28	38.9
	46 & above	26	36.1
Gender	Male	72	100%
Net Income		Frequency	Percent
	Rs. 2.1 lakhs - Rs. 5 lakhs	30	41.7
	Rs. 5.1 lakhs - Rs. 8 lakhs	41	56.9
	More than Rs. 8.1 lakhs	1	1.4
No. of years in business		Frequency	Percent
	2.1 years - 5 years	6	8.3
	5.1 years - 8 years	28	38.9
	More than 8.1 years	58	52.8

Research objective 1: To know the Preference of Traditional Vs. digital marketing channel among the kitchenware retailers in Hubli.

Table 2: Preference for Marketing Channel

	Frequency	Percent(%)
Traditional marketing channels	26	36.1%
Digital marketing channels	0	0
Both	46	63.9%

63.9%, which is majority of the respondents prefer Both Traditional and Digital Marketing Channels for their business and 36.1% prefer only Traditional Marketing. No respondent prefers only Digital Marketing. (Refer Table No.2)

Research objective 2: To know the Awareness of digital marketing among the kitchenware retailers in Hubli.

**Table 3:
Aware of Digital Marketing platforms**

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Facebook	72	100 %
Flipkart	72	100 %
Instagram	72	100 %
Whatsapp	72	100 %
Amazon	70	97.2 %
OLX	69	95.8 %
Website	64	88.9 %
E-mail	62	86.1 %
Twitter	57	79.2 %
Snap deal	40	55.6 %
Quikr	30	41.7 %
Ebay	27	37.5 %
LinkedIn	20	27.8 %
Any other	1	1.4 %

Table 4: Aware of Digital Marketing

Frequency	Percent (%)
58	80.6

80.6% (Table 4) of the respondents are aware of digital marketing. 100% of the respondents are aware that Facebook, Flipkart, Instagram and Whatsapp can be used for the business and 97.2% are aware of amazon and so on (Refer Table No. 3).

Research objective 3: To know the presence and penetration of digital marketing among the kitchenware retailers in Hubli.

Table 5: Using of Digital Marketing

Frequency	Percent (%)
26	36.1%

There are only 36.1% of the respondents, who responded that they are using Digital Marketing and the rest 63.9% of respondents are using regular Traditional Marketing.

Table 6: Using E-commerce Sites

	Frequency	Percent(%)
Flipkart	14	19.4 %
Amazon	10	13.9%
OLX	5	6.9%
Any other	1	1.4%

There are 19.4% of the respondents who were using Flipkart, 13.9% were using Amazon and 6.9% of the respondents were using OLX for their business. The respondents had used one or more than one E-commerce sites for their business. (Refer Table No. 6).

Table 7: Using Social Media/ Digital platform and frequency of updating

In percent (%)	Do not update	As per convenience
Justdial website	54.17%	1.39%
Web listing	50%	1.39%
Facebook	1.39%	20.83%
Instagram	1.39%	22.22%
Whatsapp		4.17%
Any other	1.39%	

About 54.17% and 50% of the respondents are using Just dial website and web listing as a marketing channel, but they do not update them (Refer Table No. 7). The Respondents had used one or more than one Social Media/ Digital Platforms for their business (Refer Table No. 7).

**Table 8:
How Digital Marketing is conducted**

	Frequency	Percent(%)
Self	26	36.1 %
Digital marketing partner	-	-
Hired any digital marketer	-	-

The 36.1% of the respondents (Table 5), who responded that they are using digital marketing, are conducting Digital Marketing by self. They are not hiring or partnered with any of the digital marketing partner (Refer Table No. 8).

Table 9: Usage of Digital platforms by the respondents, who responded they are using of Digital Marketing.

	Updating frequency of digital platforms	Frequency	Percent (%)
Justdial website	Do not update	25	34.72
	As per convenience	1	1.39
Web listing	Do not update	23	31.94
	As per convenience	1	1.39
Instagram	As per convenience	16	22.22
Facebook	As per convenience	15	20.83
Whatsapp	As per convenience	3	4.17

The respondents have used one or more than one Digital Marketing Platforms for promotions of their business, platforms like Web listing, Facebook, Instagram, etc. There is no respondent who update their digital platforms on daily, weekly, and monthly or on yearly basis. The respondents have no knowledge of updating information frequently on Digital Platforms, which could yield more business by usage of Digital Platforms as they either do not update or update as per their convenience.

Table 10: Usage of Social media/ Digital Platforms by the respondents who responded they are not using of Digital Marketing.

	Updating frequency of digital platforms	Frequency	Percent (%)
Justdial website	Do not update	14	19.44
Web listing	Do not update	13	18.06
Facebook	Do not update	1	1.39
Instagram	Do not update	1	1.39
Any other	Do not update	1	1.39

Unknowingly the respondents have used Digital Marketing Platforms for promotions but they earlier responded that they are not using Digital marketing. The respondents have used Digital Platforms like Web listing, Facebook, Instagram,

etc. for promotions. This means they don't know what digital marketing means because digital platforms come under digital marketing.

Table 11: Outcome from using Digital Marketing

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Increase in sales	16	22.2 %
Increase in awareness	9	12.5 %
No outcome	9	12.5 %
Increase in customers	6	8.3 %
Any Other		

The respondents who used Digital Marketing Platform were further asked about the various outcomes achieved by using Digital Platforms, the respondents have chosen multiple preferences like increase in sales, increase in awareness, etc. as their primary outcomes of using Digital Platforms.

Table 12: Expenditure on Digital Marketing

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Not Applicable	46	63.9 %
No Expenditure	26	36.1 %

As per the Table-12, None of the respondents are spending on Digital Marketing.

Research objective 4: To know the reason for usage or non-usage of Digital Marketing among the kitchenware retailers in Hubli

Table 13: Reason for using Digital Marketing

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Increases sales	26	36.1 %
Increases customers	24	33.3 %
Increases awareness	24	33.3 %
Reach to large number of people	9	12.5 %
Any Other		

Table 13 shows that respondents have one or more than one objectives or reasons for using digital marketing for their business.

Table 14: Reason for not using Digital Marketing

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Not useful for your business	36	50 %
Don't know to use	34	47.2 %
No Returns	31	43.1 %
Not aware of digital marketing	3	4.2 %
Expensive	0	0
Any other	-	-

Table 14 shows reasons why the respondents are not using Digital Marketing. The respondents have chosen one or more than one reasons for not using Digital Marketing.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no association between Preference of Digital Marketing vs. Traditional Marketing and using of Digital Marketing.

H1: There is association between Preference of Digital Marketing vs. Traditional Marketing and using of Digital Marketing.

Pearson Chi-Square test value was 0.000, which is below the standard value of 0.05; Therefore, H0 cannot be accepted. It is observed that a respondent, who prefer only Traditional Marketing, don't use Digital Marketing and a respondent, who prefer both Traditional Marketing and Digital Marketing, use Digital Marketing.

Findings

- 63.9% of the respondents responded that they prefer both Traditional and Digital Marketing Channels, but only 36.1% are using Digital Marketing.
- There are 19.4% of the respondents who responded that they are not aware of Digital Marketing, but they are aware various Digital Marketing platforms like Flipkart, Facebook, etc.
- There are 19.4% and 18.06% of the respondents who said they are not using Digital Marketing, but responded that they are using Justdial Website and Web listing respectively.
- The respondents (36.1%), who are using Digital Marketing, conduct digital marketing by themselves.

- 36.1% of the respondents who have objective to increase sales for using Digital Marketing, but only 22.2% had increase in their sales.
- 33.3% of the respondents who had an objective to increase customers by using Digital Marketing, but only 8.3% has increased in their sales.
- 33.3% of the respondents had an objective to increase awareness for using Digital Marketing, but only 12.5% has increased in their sales.
- 33.3% of the respondents don't have any
- Outcome from the usage of Digital Marketing.

Suggestions

63.9% of the respondents are using Traditional marketing channels, so these Kitchen appliance retailers need to opt for Digital Marketing to grow their business. As only 36.1% of the Kitchen appliance retailers in Hubli are using Digital Marketing, which used on a smaller scale, they need to start using Digital Marketing on Large scale. The Kitchenware appliances retailers need to understand what Digital Marketing means, because there are 19.4%, who responded that they are not using Digital Marketing, but they are using Digital platforms like Just Dial and Web listing. The respondents using Digital Marketing, conduct Digital Marketing by self, so if they hire or partner with Digital marketer/agency, they can get an expert advice, which can help them to grow their business. 12.5% of the respondents, who are using Digital Marketing, have no outcome from using Digital Marketing; this means they don't know how to use Digital Marketing effectively and efficiently, so they should know about how to use Digital Marketing effectively and efficiently.

Conclusion

The kitchen appliance retailers, who are using Digital Marketing, are using it on a small scale, which means the penetration of the Digital Marketing is low in the retail Kitchen Appliance Industry at Hubli. The retailers, who are using Digital Marketing, had increase their sales, customers and awareness, but still there are respondents who have no outcome from the usage of digital marketing. The Kitchen Appliance retailers need to know the Pros and Cons of using Digital Marketing and also need to understand how to use Digital Marketing for their business with high efficiency and effectiveness. This research was done with the intension to survey the whole population of the research in Hubli, but due

to non-availability and resisting in responding to the questionnaire by the Owners/managers only 72 respondents were surveyed. The population had no female, which could have an impact on the responses and analysis of the data.

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